

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Phenol in Polluted Waters via Oxidative Coupling using *o*-Tolidine

(MISS) PRATIMA VERMA and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010

Manuscript received 28 October 1981, revised 30 August 1982, accepted 28 April 1983

An extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination of submicrograms of phenol is described. The method involves the use of oxidative coupling reaction of phenol and *o*-tolidine using potassium dichromate-ferricyanide as an oxidizer in a buffered medium of sodium carbonate ($pH \sim 11.5$). The violet indaniline dye formed is extractable in higher alcohols. The purple coloured *iso*-amyl alcohol extract has an absorption maxima at 535 nm. Beer's law is followed in the range 10 to 70 μg of phenol (0.1 to 0.7 ppm) in a 100 ml sample. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.004 \mu g \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The optimum conditions for colour reaction and the effect of interferences have been studied. The method has been applied for the analysis of phenol in polluted river water.

PHENOLS are highly toxic and are found in the effluent from various industries. Their presence is detrimental for aquatic plants and fishes. They also affect the water quality by forming foul smelling chlorophenols¹⁻⁴. The threshold limit value for phenolic compounds is 1.0 μg /litre in domestic water and 5 mg/litre for other water, as recommended by E.P.A. of U.S.⁵. Analysis of water for phenol content is necessary before using it for domestic and irrigation purposes.

Several spectrophotometric methods have been reported for the determination of microgram amounts of phenol⁶⁻¹⁴. The most commonly used methods make use of 4-aminoantipyrine⁶, 2,6-dibromoquinone chloride⁷, *p*-aminodimethylaniline¹³ and *p*-nitroaniline¹⁴. The above methods use reagents which are either difficult to prepare, expensive or unstable in solution or the methods are time consuming.

An extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination of phenol is described in this paper. The method is based on the oxidative coupling reaction of *o*-tolidine (4,4'-bi-*o*-toluidine) and phenol, using potassium dichromate-ferricyanide couple as an oxidizer in sodium carbonate buffer medium ($pH 11.0-11.5$). The violet coloured indaniline dye formed is extractable in *iso*-pentanol, exhibits an absorption maxima at 535 nm and is stable for 24 hr. The reaction is highly selective and sensitive for phenol.

The reaction, on the basis of Vittum and Brown¹⁵, may be written as Scheme 1.

Experimental

Reagents :

Standard phenol solution : A stock solution containing 1 mg/ml phenol was prepared in deaerated glass distilled water. This solution was standardized by bromate-bromide method⁸. A working solution containing 10 μg /ml of phenol was prepared daily by appropriate dilution of the stock with deaerated glass distilled water.

Oxidizer (dichromate-ferricyanide solution) : 0.15 M stock solution was prepared by dissolving 4.47 g sodium dichromate dihydrate, 4.84 g potassium ferricyanide and 4.0 g sodium hydroxide pellets in 100 ml glass distilled water. 1.0 ml of the stock solution was diluted to 49 ml for use as working solution (0.003 M)¹⁶.

Buffer solution : 5.62 g sodium carbonate was dissolved in 500 ml glass distilled water. The pH of the solution was ~ 11.5 .

***o*-Tolidine solution ;** 0.1 M stock was prepared by dissolving 0.530 g of *o*-tolidine in 25 ml 20%

Scheme:1

*Author for correspondence.

ethanol. The stock was diluted appropriately to make a 1×10^{-3} M working solution.

EDTA solution: A 10% (w/v) aqueous solution was used.

Solution of interferents: Solutions of foreign ions were prepared by the method of West¹⁶.

All solutions were made from analytical reagent grade chemicals.

Apparatus:

Carl Ziess Spekol and ECIL Spectrophotometer, model GS 865 were used for all spectral measurements using 1.0 cm path length glass cells. pH measurements were made with ECIL digital pH meter, type pH 5651.

Procedure:

An aliquot (~100 ml) of water containing 10-70 µg (0.1-0.7 ppm) of phenol was taken in a 250 ml separatory funnel and 3 ml of dichromate-ferricyanide oxidizer was added. The pH of this solution was maintained between 11.0-11.5 by the addition of sodium carbonate buffer. After adding 3 ml *o*-tolidine solution, the separatory funnel was shaken vigorously and kept for 1-2 min. The purple coloured dye formed was extracted in 2 aliquots with 25 ml *iso*-amyl alcohol. The purple coloured extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and absorbance was measured at 535 nm against the reagent blank. The concentration of phenol was determined from a calibration curve prepared in a similar manner.

Results and Discussion

Phenol determinations were performed according to the described procedure, taking 100 ml of sample. It was found that phenol can be readily estimated in the concentration range 10^{-6} to 10^{-5} molar. Higher concentrations may be determined by appropriate dilutions. The *iso*-amyl alcohol extract of the dye shows no change in absorbance upto 24 hr and constant absorbance values were obtained in the temperature range 20 to 50°.

The optimum conditions for oxidative coupling and full colour development:

Effect of pH:

It was found that maximum absorbance was obtained at pH 11.0-11.5. The oxidation reaction was incomplete at lower pH and low absorbance values were obtained. Sodium carbonate was used for obtaining the required pH.

Effect of oxidizing solutions:

3 ml oxidizing solution was sufficient for the determination of 0.3 ppm phenol. An excess of oxidizer changed the colour of the extract from purple to brownish purple but the absorbance remained unchanged at 535 nm. Out of the various oxidizing agents tried, i.e. potassium permanganate, potassium dichromate and potassium ferricyanite, potassium dichromate-ferricyanide mixture was found to be superior to either oxidant taken alone.

Amount of *o*-tolidine solution:

Constant absorbance values were obtained by using 1:1 to 1:10 mole ratio of phenol to *o*-tolidine. 5 M excess of *o*-tolidine was used in subsequent measurements.

Effect of time and temperature:

Minimum time for full colour development, after coupling, was 1 min. Constant absorbance values were obtained in the range of 1-30 min. The absorbance remained unchanged when the reaction was carried out in the range 20-50°. However, all experiments were performed at room temperature, i.e. $30 \pm 5^\circ$.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and reproducibility:

The colour reaction was found to obey Beer's law in the range 0.1-0.7 ppm at 535 nm, extracted from 100 ml of deionized water. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction were found out to be 2.3×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.004 µg cm⁻², respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by replicate analysis of a working standard solution of phenol containing 10 µg of phenol per ml over a period of 7 days. The results obtained showed that the method is reproducible and the data obtained was employed to compute standard deviation and relative standard deviation. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.005 and $\pm 0.071\%$, respectively.

Effects of interferents:

A study was carried out to see the effect of interferents commonly present in potable water and polluted river water. The effect was studied by taking samples of water and by adding known amount of interferents commonly present in them to 100 ml water containing known quantity of phenol (Table 1). The tolerance limits of interferents are the amount of interferents that cause $\leq \pm 2\%$ error in the determination of proposed amount of phenol. Masking of ions with EDTA solution increases the tolerance limit to a considerable extent. *Para*-substituted phenols, i.e. *p*-cresol, *p*-chloro-, *p*-amino- and *p*-nitrophenol do not interfere. *Ortho* and *meta* substituted phenols cause interference when present in excess. Interference from formaldehyde and

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF INTERFERENTS
(Concentration of phenol = 0.3 ppm)

Interferents	Tolerance limit (ppm)
Hg ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	10
Zn ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Ag ⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Sb ³⁺ , As ³⁺ , B ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺	50
I ⁻ , Br ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , F ⁻	50
CH ₃ COO ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , SiO ₃ ²⁻	500
Aniline, benzene, formaldehyde, pyridine	50
<i>p</i> -Cresol, <i>p</i> -chlorophenol, <i>p</i> -nitrophenol	100
<i>o</i> -Cresol, <i>m</i> -cresol	60
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol, <i>m</i> -nitrophenol	50
Sulphur dioxide	70
Hydrogen sulphide	50

aromatic amines, suspected to be present in industrial waste water, can be removed by distillation of phenol before analysis by the recommended procedures¹⁷. Sulphur containing compounds and oxidizing materials which interfere in routine analysis were also removed by the standard procedure⁸.

Comparison with conventional method⁸ :

The present method can be favourably compared with other common⁶⁻¹⁴ methods used for the determination of phenols. The analytical values, obtained from conventional methods were compared with those obtained by the proposed method for polluted river water samples, are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RIVER WATER ANALYSIS*

Proposed method phenol + <i>o</i> -tolidine (ppm)	Conventional method ⁸ 4-aminoantipyrine (ppm)
15.10	15.15
14.70	14.73
13.05	13.01
11.10	11.15
10.78	10.70
6.06	6.08
5.35	5.33
4.80	4.82
2.28	2.30
3.80	3.84

* Mean of 3 replicates.

The proposed method is found to be more rapid, simple, sensitive and the dye formed is far more stable. The method is used for the determination of submicrograms of phenol present in polluted river water.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for laboratory facilities.

References

1. F. A. PATTY, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", V. II, 2nd Edn., Interscience Publishers, New York, 1963.
2. Environmental Protection Agency, "Quality Criteria For Water" Superintendent of Documents, U. S. Printing Office, Washington D. C., 1976.
3. W. LEITHE, "The Analysis of Organic Pollutants in Water and Waste Waters", Ann Arbor Science Publishers, Ann Arbor, Michigan, 1959.
4. National Academy of Science and National Academy of Engineering, Water Quality Criteria (1972), "A Report of the Committee of Water Quality Control", Environmental Studies Board, Superintendent of Documents, U. S. Printing Office, Order No. 5501-00520, Washington D. C.
5. Environmental Protection Agency, "Manual of Methods for Chemical Analysis of Water and Waste Waters", Office of Technology Transfer, Washington D. C., 1974.
6. R. G. SMITH, J. D. MCEWEN and R. E. BARROW, *J. Amer. Ind. Hyg. Association*, 1959, 20, 142.
7. H. D. GIBBS, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1949, 72, 649.
8. "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Waters", Amer. Public Health Assocn., Inc., 14th Edn., 1975, 574.
9. E. G. MOHLER, JR. and L. N. JACOB, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, 29, 1369.
10. H. D. FRIESTED, D. E. OTT and F. A. GUNTHER, "Advances in Automat. Analysis", Technicon, International Congress, 1969, McClid, New York, 1970.
11. Z. REGNIER and A. E. D. WASTON, Water Quality Division Research Report, Department of the Environment, Ottawa, 1971.
12. M. J. MURRAY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 941.
13. D. N. KRAMER and L. U. TOLENTINO, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 834.
14. N. L. ALLPORT and J. E. BROCKSHOPS, "Colorimetric Analysis", 2nd Edn., Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1963, 239.
15. P. W. VITUM and G. H. BROWN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2235.
16. P. W. WEST, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1941, 18, 528.
17. G. NORWITZ and P. N. KELIHAR, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 119, 99.